

EUROPT(R)ODE XVII

JENA | GERMANY | March 29 – April 1, 2026

ABSTRACTS & POSTERS

www.europtrode2026.eu

Plasmonics and Quantum-Enhanced Optical Sensing III

Optimization of Silver-Coated Boehmite Nanostructures for Enhanced SERS Detection of Date-rape Drugs

G. Geka¹, F. Kalogeropoulou¹, A. Kanioura¹, M. Angelopoulou¹, S. Richardson², A. Dimitriou², D. Tsounidi³, I. Raptis³, D. Goustouridis³, N. Papanikolaou², S. Kakabakos¹, P. Petrou¹

1) Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences & Technology, Energy & Safety, NCSR "Demokritos, Agia Paraskevi, Greece, email: ypetrou@rrp.demokritos.gr

2) Institute of Nanoscience & Nanotechnology, NCSR "Demokritos", Agia Paraskevi, Greece

3) ThetaMetrisis S.A., 12132, Athens, Greece

Metallic nanostructured surfaces significantly enhance the Raman signal intensity of molecules immobilized on them [1]. This detection approach, known as Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS), has expanded the application range of Raman spectroscopy into biosensing due to its minimal susceptibility to matrix interferences. To fully exploit SERS for biosensing applications, substrates with high enhancement factors, uniformity over large areas, and facile, reproducible fabrication are required.

In the present work, silicon surfaces coated with an aluminium layer were subjected to thermal treatment in an aqueous environment to partially oxidize the aluminium, generating boehmite nanostructures. Silver was then deposited onto these nanostructures by sputtering to produce the SERS substrates [2]. Substrates prepared using different silver deposition parameters on the boehmite nanostructures (Figure 1) were evaluated in terms of their signal enhancement factors using Rhodamine 6G and uric acid as model analytes with well-characterized Raman spectra. The performance of the prepared substrates was also compared to that of commercially available SERS substrates bearing silver or gold nanostructures.

It was found that substrates with silver layers between 40 and 80 nm achieved enhancement factors exceeding 10^7 for both Rhodamine 6G and uric acid. In both cases, the enhancement factors were significantly higher than those obtained with commercial substrates. Subsequently, the substrates were employed for the detection of γ -hydroxybutyric acid (GHB), a substance frequently associated with drug-facilitated sexual assault due to its ability to induce loss of consciousness. Its precursor compound, γ -butyrolactone (GBL), was also detected, as it is often administered instead of GHB. The optimum deposited silver thickness was determined to be 60 nm, and concentrations as low as 0.1 mg/mL could be detected, compared to the typically administered dose (1–4 mg/mL). A compact device for SERS measurements has also been developed, aiming to provide an on-site detection tool for GHB and GBL in beverages.

Figure 1. SEM images of boehmite coated Si chips a) prior to and b) after sputtering of Ag.

Acknowledgment: This research has been financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101168416 (ARMADILLO).

References:

- [1] D. Cialla-May, A. Bonifacio, A. Markin, N. Markina, S. Fornasaro, A. Dwivedi, T. Dib, E. Farnesi, C. Liu, A. Ghosh, M. Schmitt, J. Popp, *TrAC Trend Anal. Chem.*, 181, 117990 (2024).
- [2] A. Dimitriou, A.S. Kastania, P. Sarkiris, V. Shvalya, N. Papanikolaou, U. Cvelbar, E. Gogolides, *Micro Nano Eng.*, 24, 100279 (2024).